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Performance of E-government in China during the outbreak of COVID-19

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E-government means that government agencies rely on ICTs to optimize and reorganize government workflow and organization to realize governmental governance and services online. Scholars have argued that E-government has the potential to increase the transparency of government institutions, assist citizens in gaining access to public information, and expand their engagement in democratic processes (Netchaeva 2002; Lenihan 2002; Ndou 2004). E-government has a favorable impact on participatory democracy, directly and indirectly, as it increases the potential for controlling corruption, openness, and accountability (Bekkers et al., 2007; Dunleavy et al., 2006; Sami et al., 2021). Globally, governments have been pressured to embrace E-Government initiatives to increase government-citizen communication (Van der Meer et al., 2014). Citizens demand more effective service delivery as they connect with government services online (Kaisara and Pather 2009). Through E-government, the government and citizens engage in a two-way interaction, with citizens being able to transmit and receive information via the internet, thereby improving the delivery of government services (Huai 2011). This research evaluates the performance of E-government on the realization of public value, especially the problem-solving capacity, including Democratic Consultation, Participation, and Accountability during the outbreak of COVID-19 in China; also, along the problem-solving path, the elements of Responsiveness, Openness, Transparency, Equality, Convenience, and Timeliness could be assessed.

This research uses Python to mine the data of citizens' messages to governors/mayors of 10 regions from the "Message Board for Local Leaders (MBLL, 领导留言板)" and governors/mayors' responses and solutions to examine the performance of the E-government. This research focuses on 10 selected provinces: Guangdong Province, Zhejiang Province, Hubei Province, Jiangsu Province, Guizhou Province, Hebei Province, Guangxi Province, Chongqing, Beijing, and Shanghai, with data distribution from January 1, 2020, to December 31, 2021, to test the public value of E-government after COVID-19, whether E-government can bring good governance or not. These provinces and regions are selected because they include different areas in the east, central, west, south, and north of China, and regions with typical government big data governance models. Choosing data from 2020 to

2021 is to observe the variability between regions in the government's effectiveness in using big data governance platforms to respond to citizens' needs and address their problems when COVID-19 was at its worst, and in 2021 when the pandemic was less severe.

By carrying out this research, we will know that E-government platforms allow Chinese netizens to interact directly with local governments to solve real-life problems during the COVID-19 period. Additionally, the network's diverse and convenient expression allows citizens to participate in governmental big data governance and strengthens E-democracy. However, E-government still has many shortcomings in the emergency management process.

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